

A Comment on “Extent of Sound Image Lateralization: Influence of Measurement Method”

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Comment

On page 751 of [1], we wrote with respect to data presented in Figure 2: “...there is a difference in reported lateralization between the filtered and broad-band stimuli using the acoustic pointer but not in the direct pointing results. It has previously been shown that the localization percept adapts to preceding distractors... We therefore hypothesized that differences in the lateralization results obtained from the direct pointing and the acoustic pointing procedures stem from an interaction between the target and pointer stimuli in the acoustic pointer paradigm.”

After publication, Dr. Leslie R. Bernstein brought to our attention that, for a given ITD of e.g., 0.6 ms, there is, indeed, a difference in perceived lateralization between the filtered and the broad-band click-train in a direct comparison of the two types of stimuli. While it was not tested in a formal measurement, for the authors and for Dr. Bernstein, the broad-band stimulus is perceived more lateral compared to the band-pass filtered. This observation offers an alternative and arguably more plausible explanation than what we provided in the publication: There is a difference in extent of lateralization for the two different stimuli and it is reflected in the results of the acoustic pointer method but not the visual reference method.

An additional conclusion to our study is therefore, that the direct pointing method and its use of a visual reference scale is not necessarily as precise with respect to revealing differences in extent of laterality as is the acoustic pointer method. This observation has no direct implication for the interpretation of the other data in the paper.

References

- [1] R. M. Baumgärtel, M. Dietz: Extent of sound image lateralization: influence of measurement method. *Acta Acustica united with Acustica* **104** (2018) 748–752.

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